

SERVICE CONVENIENCE AND CUSTOMER LOYALTY OF MONEY DEPOSIT BANKS IN PORT HARCOURT

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ABSTRACT:

This study was carried out primarily to investigate the relationship between service convenience and customer loyalty in money deposit banks in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The cross-sectional survey research design was adopted for the study. The target population of study was 55,000 bank customers, with 397 determined as the sample size using Taro Yamen's formula for sample size determination from a finite population. Primary data was utilized in the study. Primary data were collected with a well-structured questionnaire and administered to the bank customers in Port Harcourt. The questionnaire was validated through face and content validity. Statistical tools for data analyses included descriptive analysis and The Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC). Major findings show that the three dimensions of service convenience (perceived quality, service fairness and availability) had strong and significant relationship with the two measures of customer loyalty (referral and repeat purchase) in money deposit banks in Port Harcourt. The study concluded that service convenience impacts on customer loyalty of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that money deposit banks should constantly interact with their customers and also create an environment that fair and free from manipulation.

KEYWORDS:

Service Convenience. Perceived Quality. Service Fairness. Availability. Referral. Repeat Purchase.

Introduction

The uncertainty created by the transformations brought about by globalization makes it necessary for the service industry to produce more value and to rapidly adapt to those changes. We are living in a century of idea diffusion: “People that spread ideas, regardless of what those ideas are, win.” It is not what is offered that is of importance, but how it is marketed (Godin, 2003).

Nigeria deposit money banks operate in a dynamic environment, hence their activities are constantly adjusting to the changing needs and aspiration of all stakeholders. The political, socio-economic and cultural changes have made deposit money banks to create value of shareholders’ wealth without undermining its costs and profit. Deposit money banks (DMBs) are faced with decision of minimising costs and optimising profit. Spong, Sullivan, and DeYoung (2011) argue that increasing competition from nonbank institutions and from banks expanding into new market is putting strong pressure on banks to improve their earnings and to control costs.

Service convenience is one of the most important factors in businesses today. When it comes to money deposit banks, service convenience level differentiates one bank from another, thus meaning service convenience is exceeding important, (Zopounidis, 2012). This is the reason why banks listen to customer requirements and complain. Profitable business cannot exist without satisfied customers.

Customers loyalty and its measurements in marketing literature reveals that service quality plays a significant role. The better the service quality rendered by a bank, the more satisfied a customer is (Barlan-Espino, 2017; Ebiringa&Okorafor,2010). However, there has been limited research into the explicit linkage between service convenience, customer loyalty and financial performance in DMBs in Port Harcourt, although past research on this issue has examined a range of performance questions using a wide variety of indicators.

A satisfied customer is of great importance for the bank. Keeping a current customer faithful requires five times less effort, time and money than getting a new one. Such a customer is willing to pay higher prices, is a free form of advertising for the bank, and is inclined to purchase further products. He or she raises in bank employees a sense of satisfaction and pride in their work and business (Korauš, 2011; Titko and Lace, 2010). In this context, Bilan (2013) states that consumers don’t want to play games – if they feel that something has gone wrong, they go away and choose another supplier.

Money deposits banks in PortHarcourt has witness tremendous growth of its loan portfolio in recent years but this growth can only be attributed to a small group of customers who have been in the institution for years. Then the question of why do this group keep coming back while other leave the institution after a short spell. Numerous complaints have been received by the marketing department on quality of services. However most of these concerns and trends have not been investigated to identify causes. The measurement of satisfaction has been a relatively new concept to many banks that have been focused on income statement and balance sheets. The intense rivalry in the banking sector and the ever present headache of optimising promotional budget has necessitated marketers to come up with an anti-traditional approach in conducting a commercialisation of their services. With the intention of taking advantage of a strong market position and minimisation of cost, firms use various tactics to stay afloat.

Banks now recognise that the new global economy has changed things forever, increased competition, crowded markets with little product differentiation has meant that banks would have to take proactive measures to gain that competitive edge. Determining the level of service convenience is the initial step to gain that edge. Finding why that level of satisfaction and relating it to the current marketing strategy is the most crucial.

Customer satisfaction is very different from customer loyalty according to Vance Christensen, Co-founder and CEO of Amae Software. One is required to do business while the other is the basis for sustained profitability and growth. customer chum rates are at unprecedented highs everywhere. As markets shrinks, banks are scrambling to boost customer satisfaction and keep their current customers rather than developing additional resources to chase potential new customers. Banks in port Harcourt recognize that the new global economy has changed things forever. Banks that are prospering in the new global economy recognize that service convenience is key.

Aim and objective of the Study

The aim of this study is to ascertain the relationship between service convenience and customer loyalty of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

To achieve this the following objectives are considered. Thus;

- To determine the relationship between perceived quality and referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.
- To evaluate the relationship between service fairness and referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.
- To determine the relationship between availability and referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.
- To determine the relationship between perceived quality and repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.
- To determine the relationship between service fairness and repeat purchase of money deposits banks in Port Harcourt.
- To determine the relationship between availability and repeat purchase of money deposits banks in Port Harcourt.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: *Conceptual Framework of the study*

Source: Researcher's Desk,2023.

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses are to be tested so as to ascertain the extent of Service convenience and how it affects banks customer loyalty.

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between perceived quality and referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between perceived quality and repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between service fairness and referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between service fairness and repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Ho₅: There is no significant relationship between availability and referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

H₀₆: There is no significant relationship between availability and repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Literature Review

Theoretical Foundation

Expectancy theory (or expectancy theory of motivation):proposes that an individual will behave or act in a certain way because they are motivated to select a specific behavior over others due to what they expect the result of that selected behavior will be. In essence, the motivation of the behavior selection is determined by the desirability of the outcome. However, at the core of the theory is the cognitive process of how an individual processes the different motivational elements. This is done before making the ultimate choice. The outcome is not the sole determining factor in making the decision of how to behave.

Expectancy theory is about the mental processes regarding choice, or choosing. It explains the processes that an individual undergoes to make choices. In the study of organizational behavior, expectancy theory is a motivation theory first proposed by Victor Vroom of the Yale School of Management. This theory emphasizes the needs for organizations to relate rewards directly to performance and to ensure that the rewards provided are those rewards deserved and wanted by the recipients.

Conceptual Review

Service Convenience

Brown, (1990) defined service convenience as any ease that fascinates the customer towards that particular service such as providing it in such a manner that reduces the time and effort of the customers. Service convenience was first proposed by Copeland (1923) that the utilization of the time and both the physical and mental effort of the consumer should be minimized when they are going to purchase the product. In order to provide high quality service or the service which meets the consumer expectation, the company must have to offer the service convenience to its customers (Berry et al., 2002; Liang & Wang, 2006). Service convenience helps the organization to strengthen their relationship with their customers and achieve the competitive edge by bringing it to new position (Seiders et al., 2000).

Consumers perceive time and effort costs related to each type of service convenience. Researchers in marketing recognize that overall convenience is a second-order construct that consists of five convenience types (Berry et al., 2002; Seiders, Voss, Grewal, & Godfrey, 2005; Aagja, Mammen, & Amit, 2011; Rahman, & Parisa, 2014): decision, access, transaction, benefit, and post-benefit convenience. Decision convenience refers to the idea that consumers who desire a particular performance devote time and effort to deciding how to obtain it. Access convenience means consumers' perceived time and effort expenditures for initiating service delivery. Transaction convenience describes consumers' perceived expenditures of time and effort in effecting a transaction. Benefit convenience refers to consumers' perceived time and effort expenditures required to experience the service's core benefits, such as being transported in a taxi or watching a movie. Finally, post-benefit

convenience involves the consumer's perceived time and effort expenditures when reinitiating contact with a firm after completing the benefit stage of the service.

The reason that banks are performing well and competing in the market is that they want to satisfy their customers by fulfilling all their needs, because when the customer is happy then their business will flourish which in return, affect the profitability of the company (Shen, Tan & Xie, 2000) and earning high profit is the ultimate goal of any business (Garbarino & Johnson, 1999).

Perceived Quality: Berry et al. (1988) defined perceived quality as “conformance to customer specifications”. Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry (1988) defined perceived quality as “a global judgment or attitude, relating to the superiority of the service and explicated it as involving evaluations of the outcome”. Hoffman and Bateson (2010) defined perceived quality as an attitude formed by a long-term, overall evaluation of a firm's performance. Lovelock et al. (2011) defined perceived quality as “consistently meeting or exceeding customer expectations”. Lewis (1989) defined perceived service quality as a consumer judgment that resulted from comparisons consumer made between expectations and perceptions of the actual service performance. Perceived quality received much attention and gained importance because of its obvious relationship with cost (Kellogg et al. 1997), financial performance (Rust et al, 1994, 1995) and customer retention (Boshoff, 1997). Donabedian (2005) stated that banks profitability and client satisfaction were remarkably dependent on customers' perception of perceived quality. Andaleeb (2001) explained that perceived service quality had a positive impact on word-of-mouth and customer loyalty. According to Iacobucci et al. (1994), perceived quality was an important phenomenon for marketers. Customer's evaluation of perceived quality and the level of their satisfaction were thought to determine the likelihood of repeat purchase, finally affecting the bottom-line measures of business success.

Over the past three decades, especially in the industrialized nations the service sector has become the dominant part of the economy and the researches exposed that service quality is a precondition for success and survival in this competitive environment, the interest in perceived quality has increased conspicuously (Ghobadian et al., 1994). Therefore, different explanations have been suggested throughout the years. Nightingale (1985) explained perceived quality as an evolving individual construct of values and expectations in contradiction of which an individual evaluates a product or service. Gronroos (1984) elucidated it as the consequence of an evaluation process, where the user compares his or her expectations with the service he or she perceived and received. Parasuraman et al. (1988) clarified service quality as an attitude, associated but not equivalent to satisfaction and results from a contrast of expectations with perceptions of performance. Gummesson (1991) verified that many goods quality ideologies could be applied to the examination of service quality, as long as the “L factor: love, compassion, empathy, sense of humor, tacit knowledge, knowledge by acquaintance, and insights” are taken into account. Johns in 1992 illuminated quality contains of chains of sub-qualities or quality characteristics. Oliver (1993) defined it as the customer's perception of what service ought to be may change from what they believe they will likely receive. Ideal expectations drive quality, whereas desired expectations drive satisfaction. Brady and Cronin in 2001 confirmed that service quality is formed by three attributes: interaction quality, physical environment quality, and outcome quality; and nine sub-attributes: attitude, behavior, expertise, ambient conditions, design, social factors, waiting time, tangibles, and valence.

Service Fairness: The concept of fairness is rooted in the theory of justice, which is in turn adapted from equity theory (Adams, 1965), suggesting that over-rewarded and under-rewarded relationship outcomes cause distress that people strive to reduce. Individuals are seeking a fair input/output balance and become satisfied whenever they feel their inputs are fairly rewarded. Perception of unfairness can lead to distress and dissatisfaction. In contrast, perception of fairness results in positive emotions and satisfaction (Patterson et al., 1997; Szymanski and Henard, 2001).

Service fairness or justice is understood across three dimensions: distributive, procedural and interactional fairness (Yen et al., 2010). Distributive fairness (DF) involves price in relation to the outcome of the service delivered and reflects customers' perceptions of the benefits and cost balance among parties. Procedural fairness is about exchange relationships and is associated with the elements of impartiality, refutability, explanation and familiarity of service personnel. Last but not least, interactional fairness (IF) deals with the fairness of interpersonal treatment and refers to: a) courtesy, respect and consideration shown by service representatives during the transaction and b) the extent and quality of mutual communication.

Availability: Availability represents the ability of services to be accessible as needed, whenever and wherever they are required. Service availability is the characteristic of a resource that is committable, operable, or usable upon demand to perform its designated or required function. It is the aggregate of the resource's accessibility, reliability, maintainability, serviceability, and securability. Service availability is an important factor to consumers in the banking sector.

Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty has been the popular topic among the business workplaces (Leong et al 2012) and recent years have shown a growing interest in customer loyalty (Kuusik 2007) so has been widely researched in the domain of marketing (BOSE and RAO 2011). Loyalty is a positive belief in the value that a company provides, leading to increased purchases over time. Oliver (1999, p.33) defines loyalty as "a deeply held commitment to rebuild and re-patronize a preferred product or service in the future despite situational influences and marketing efforts having the potential to cause switching behaviors". Loyalty building requires the company to focus the value of its product and services and to show that it is interested to fulfill the desire or build the relationship with customers (Griffin 2002).

Motivation has a powerful part to play in the success of customer loyalty. It makes customers want to engage more if they know they'll get something valuable in return. This desire ties a lot into expectancy theory: that an individual will behave they're motivated by a desirable results. You need to show customers why your bank is worth the effort and how they'll get rewarded for engaging with you.

Referral: It can be referred as the oral, person to person communication between a receiver and the communicator whom the receiver perceived as non-commercial, regarding a brand, product or service (Arndt, 1967). Stern (1994) defined that word of mouth (WOM) is gotten by drawing on its distinctiveness from advertising. Unlike advertising, WOM differs in its lack of boundaries. Hermann and Fuerderer (1997) asserted that referral is seen as individual customer contribution to the service provider goals due to the satisfaction he/she derived from the service.

Repeat Purchase: Repeat purchase describes a purchase situation whereby a customer or an individual willingly re-patronizes a particular vendor/shop or service organization (Writz & Lwin, 2009). Repeat purchase is usually referred to as re-patronage intention. A customer who makes a repeat purchase from a particular vendor is aware of the available service which a service provider offers. It is expected that the purchaser/customer must have been satisfied by the previous transaction and desires to make a further purchase of the product (goods or services) and/or new product. We expect that a firm can achieve customer loyalty, if a customer is satisfied with a firm's offering (product/service) and purchase process.

Service Convenience and Customer Loyalty

The goal of money deposit banks should be to position itself in the same strategy while offering superior value compared to rival offerings (Richard, Foster and Morgan 1998; Harris and Chernatony, 2001), such as service convenience (Berry et al., 2002). Customers seeking service convenience are going to pay a premium for the bank offering service convenience. Some empirical findings indicate that convenience including both location and service process convenience is significantly related to customer loyalty. (Brown 1990; Andaleeb & Basu, 1994; Keaveney, 1995; Rust, Katherine, & Zeithaml, 2004; Seiders et al., 2005).

The second-order construct of service convenience reflects the stages of consumers' activities as related to buying or using a service (Berry et al., 2002, Seiders et al., 2005). Moreover, consumers' perceived time and effort costs relate to each type of service convenience, thereby affecting consumers' overall convenience evaluations (Seiders et al., 2000; Pura, 2005; Aagja, Mammen, & Amit, 2011; Gupta, & Sharma, 2014; Rahman, & Parisa, 2014). Yen and Gwinner (2003) propose that increased service convenience in the form of providing access to services should have a positive influence on perceptions of special treatment benefits.

The money deposit bank that offers a convenient service helps consumers reduce costs not only by establishing an enduring and valued relationship, but also by creating a desire to visit a specific money deposit bank whose service convenience is better than its competitors (Ailawadi & Keller, 2004; Hunt, Geiger-Oneto, & Varca, 2012). This when the money deposit banks demonstrates service convenience, consumers develop continuance and affective commitment.

Perceived Quality and Customer Loyalty

The meaning of perceived quality is regarded as a significantly important study for all researchers and marketing managers. It is becoming a vital role to make a difference from competitors with the products and service's quality between the brand and customers. Service convenience uses perceived quality as one of its potent weapons to drive its idea to prospects. Every firm that uses service convenience wants to achieve a perceived quality from the point of view of the customers. There is a value relationship between perceived value and satisfaction recommended by Cronin and Hult (2000). The perceived quality is defined as the consumer's perception of the overall components of a product or service including tangible and intangible values. It may also include performance, features, reliability, conformance, durability, serviceability, and aesthetics etc. Perceived quality is a bridge between the business organization and customer in the service interaction. For example, when the business organization creates the good quality of services or products, their consumer will

feel happy; then they continue to buy again their services or products. Therefore, perceived quality contributes to customer loyalty. From the foregoing, it was hypothesized that;

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between perceived quality and referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between perceived quality and repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Service Fairness and Customer loyalty

Service fairness is based on equity theory which argues that people are motivated when they compare the ratio of their inputs to received outcomes with that of the others. Customers want the procedures to be unbiased and not excessively favoring any individual or group in distributing the service resources. The study of Chebata and Slusarczyk's, depict that perceptions of people regarding equal distribution have a significant positive effect on their relationship with service providers. Similarly, study of Ambrose et al, illustrate that people look for fair & consistent service and that unfair treatment leads towards customer complaints. Moreover, customers are satisfied if they receive similar services that are provided to the others. All customers want to be heard and not looked down on, they want a fair service. There is a positive relationship between service fairness and customer loyalty. From the foregoing, it was hypothesized that;

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between service fairness and referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between service fairness and repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Availability and customer loyalty

At its most basic level, availability is an organization ability to supply their customers wants and needs. Service availability is the number one driving force behind the banking sector, and most business owners understand that the relationship between service availability and customer loyalty is very simple. If proper services are available your customers will be happy and will keep coming back: if there's no available service, you shouldn't expect customers to feel any devotion towards your business. The quality of available services directly influences customers' loyalty. From the foregoing, it was hypothesized that;

H₀₅: There is no significant relationship between availability and referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

H₀₆: There is no significant relationship between availability and repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Research Methodology

In view of the nature and purpose of this research, this study employed the cross-sectional survey research method. It is worthy to note that research population involves a group of persons or aggregate items/ things a researcher is interested in getting information from, in order to execute his investigations or study (Nzeneri, 2011). Currently there are 23 deposit money banks dispersed round Port Harcourt with their massive and inaccessible customer base. However, for the sake of ease, the researcher streamlined the target radar to 55,000 customers.

The probability sampling technique was adopted for this study using a simple random technique because it gives all elements of the accessible population the equal chance of being selected. Following the assertion of Richard and Yunonne(2005), our target population (N) is 55000 customers. The sample size of the study that constitutes a proper representation of the elements of the population is determined using a Taro Yamen's formula with a significant level of 95% (0.05); the formula is stated mathematically thus;

Taro Yamen Formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where:

n = the sample size

N = estimated size of the population of interest

1 = theoretical constant

e = the level of significance...(0.05)

Thus:

$$n = \frac{55000}{1 + 55000 * (0.05^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{55000}{1 + 55000 * (0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{55000}{1 + 137.5}$$

$$n = \frac{55000}{1 + 138.5}$$

$$n = 397$$

The data used for this research were obtained from primary source with the use of questionnaire for data collection. The instrument used in collecting data from respondents was designed in three distinct sections: sections A, B & C. Section A involves the respondents' demographics, section B bordered on the independent variable, while section C are questions emanating from the dependent variable.

In order to satisfy the objective of the study which involves evaluating relationships between variables of the study, correlation model is considered appropriate since representation entails determination of relationship among variables. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used. Thus,

$$R = \frac{N(E_{xy}) - (E_x)(E_y)}{\sqrt{(N(E_{x^2}) - (E_x)^2)(N(E_{y^2}) - (E_y)^2)}}$$

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 21 would be used to analyze the relationship between the variables. Previously, we have explored the critical presentation of all the data generated from the field, which was later analyzed through the exhaustive application of SPSS window output. Such text as descriptive, frequencies, percentages of data were carried out.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Questionnaire Response Rate

Table 1: Administration and Retrieval of Questionnaire

S/N	NAMES OF BANKS	Questionnaire Administered	Copies Retrieved	Copies not Retrieved	Copies Wrongly Entered
1	Access Bank	29	22	0	5
2	Eco Bank	29	26	3	0
3	First Bank	29	24	5	3
4	Fidelity Bank	29	24	5	1
5	Guarantee Trust Bank	28	25	0	1
	Total	144	121	13	10

From the Table 1above, it is witnessed that 144 questionnaires were administered to respondents. Nonetheless, out of this number only 121 questionnaires were correctly filled and returned and thus suitable for data analysis. 3 of it was not returned.

Analysis of data

In this section, the researcher examined the personal information respondents contained in the questionnaire.

Demographic Analysis

From the data on demographic profile of respondents, 6 respondents representing 5.0 % of the respondents were less than 25 years of age, 29 respondents representing 22.3% fall within the 26-35 years' age bracket while 42 of the respondents representing 34.7 % were observed to have fallen within the 36-45 years' age bracket. The remaining 46 respondents representing 38.0% of the total respondents were 46 years and above.

In terms of marital status, 26 of the respondents representing 21.5 % of the respondents were single while the remaining 84 of the respondents representing 69.4 % were married and 11 representing 9.1 % were divorced. Based on years of patronizing their current banks, the profile revealed that 15 respondents representing 12.4 % had been customers for less than 5years. A total of 74 respondents(61.2 %) had been customers for a period between 5-10 years and 32 of the respondents representing 26.4 % had been in the system as customers for more than 10years and above.

With regard to gender, 75 representing 62.0 percent of the respondents weremales while 46 representing 38.0 percent of the respondents were females.The data depicting the educational qualifications of the respondents showed that 27 respondents representing 22.3% have

HND/BSc/B.Ed/B.Tech, 62 of the respondents representing 51.2% were master degree holders, while 32 respondents representing 26.4% are holders of Doctorate degree,

Bivariate Data Analyses (Inferential Statistics/Test of Hypothesis)

Test of Research Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between perceived quality and referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Table 2: Perceived Quality and Referral

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS 1

		Perceived Quality	Referral
Perceived Quality	Pearson Correlation	1	.873**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	121	121
Referral	Pearson Correlation	.873**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	121	121

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result in Table 2 indicated that perceived quality correlate with referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt. ($r = 0.873$, $p = 0.000 < 0.001$). This connotes a very high correlation indicating normal relationship. The relationship that exists within perceived quality and referral is shown to be significant at 0.01 significant levels. Hence the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Meaning relationship do occur.

Test of Research Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between perceived quality and repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Table 3: Perceived Quality and Repeat Purchase

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS 2

		Perceived Quality	Repeat Purchase
Perceived Quality	Pearson Correlation	1	.891**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	121	121
Repeat Purchase	Pearson Correlation	.891**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	121	121

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The outcome in Table 3 indicated that perceived quality correlate with repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt. ($r = 0.891$, $p = 0.000 < 0.001$). This connotes a very high correlation indicating normal relationship. The relationship that exists within perceived quality and repeat purchase is shown to be significant at 0.01 significant levels.

Test of Research Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between service fairness and referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Table 4: Service Fairness and Referral

TEST OF HYPOYHESIS 3

		Service Fairness	Referral
Service Fairness	Pearson Correlation	1	.940**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	121	121
Referral	Pearson Correlation	.940**	1

Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
N	121	121

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 indicates that service fairness correlate with referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt. ($r = 0.940$, $p = 0.000 < 0.001$). This connotes a very high correlation indicating normal relationship. The relationship that exists within Service Fairness and Referral is shown to be significant at 0.01 significant levels.

Test of Research Hypothesis Four

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between service fairness and repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Table 5: Service Fairness and Repeat Purchase

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS 4

		Service Fairness	Repeat Purchase
Service Fairness	Pearson Correlation	1	.869**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	121	121
Repeat Purchase	Pearson Correlation	.869**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	121	121

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The upshot in Table 5 indicated that service fairness correlate with repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt. ($r = -0.869$, $p = 0.000 < 0.001$). This connotes a very high correlation indicating normal relationship. The relationship that exists within task service fairness and repeat purchase is shown to be significant at 0.01 significant levels.

Test of Research Hypothesis Five

H₀₅: There is no significant relationship between availability and referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Table 6: Availability and Referral

TEST OF HYPOYHESIS 5

		Availability	Referral
Availability	Pearson Correlation	1	.712**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	121	121
Referral	Pearson Correlation	.712**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	121	121

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The upshot in Table 6 indicated that availability correlate with referral of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt. ($r = 0.712$, $p = 0.000 < 0.001$). This connotes a very high correlation indicating normal relationship. The relationship that exists within task availability and referral is shown to be significant at 0.01 significant levels.

Test of Research Hypothesis Six

H₀₆: There is no significant relationship between availability and repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Table 7: Availability and Repeat Purchase

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS 6

		Availability	Repeat Purchase
Availability	Pearson Correlation	1	.838**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	121	121

Repeat	Pearson Correlation	.838**	1
Purchase	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	121	121

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The upshot in Table 7 indicated that availability correlate with repeat purchase of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt. ($r = 0.838$, $p = 0.000 < 0.001$). This connotes a very high correlation indicating normal relationship. The relationship that exists within availability and repeat purchase is shown to be significant at 0.01 significant levels.

Discussion of Findings

In this section, the results of the hypothesized relationship are explained and correlated with existing literature to provide sufficient bases required for a vital contribution to existing knowledge.

In the research, hypotheses H_{o1} and H_{o2} were tested as indicated in Table 2 and 3. the result indicates that p -value=0.001, alpha value=0.001 and $p = 0.000 < 0.001$ which implies that there is a significant and positive relationship between perceived quality and customer loyalty.

Based on the above results the null hypotheses was rejected (H_{o1} and H_{o2}) and the alternate (H_{a1} and H_{a2}) was accepted. The findings however corroborate with the findings of (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2000) that through the provision of high levels of perceived quality, companies can achieve increased customer satisfaction, loyalty and therefore long-term profitability. In order to provide high level of perceived quality and therefore create value for their customers, service organizations need to plan their services and ensure the successful implementation of the actual plan.

Hypotheses H_{o3} and H_{o4} were tested as indicated in Tables 4 and 5 respectively. The results indicate that p -value=0.000, alpha value=0.001 and $p=0.000 < 0.001$ which implies that there is a significant and positive relationship between service fairness and customer loyalty. Based on the above results the null hypotheses was rejected (H_{o3} and H_{o4}) the alternate (H_{a3} and H_{a4}) was accepted, (Chebata & Slusarczyk's. 2005) customers want the procedures to be unbiased and not excessively favoring-any individual or group in distributing the service resources. Depict that perceptions of people regarding equal distribution have a significant positive effect on their relationship with service providers.

Finally, Hypotheses H_{o5} and H_{o6} were tested as indicated in Table 6 and 7 respectively. The result indicates that p -value = 0.000, alpha value = 0.001 and $p = 0.000 < 0.001$ which implies that there is a significant and positive relationship between availability and customer loyalty. This results were supported by the claims of (Irvin 2005) that availability is an integral aspect that leads to customer loyalty for businesses (money deposit banks) to remain competitive and meet customer expectations.

Conclusion

Money deposit banks exist for the purpose of providing services to its customers. These customers are key; they are the reason for the existence of any bank. As a result, banking services of any type must be packaged putting the customers into consideration in terms of springing up; it becomes paramount for banks to understand what their customers' needs are and provide them in a convenient way so the customer will be satisfied with the service. Our aim and objective was to discover the relationship existing between service convenience and customer loyalty of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt. All the stated null hypotheses were rejected, thereby accepting the alternate hypothesis. Based on this, the researcher concludes that service convenience impacts on customer loyalty of money deposit banks in Port Harcourt.

Recommendations

The study threw some light into the minds money deposit banks management with respect to the impact of service convenience on customer loyalty. The study findings give deposit money banks in Port Harcourt the opportunity to create a better loyalty programs that would benefit current and potential customers. As a result, we therefore make recommendations based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

- 1) Money deposit banks who want to improve customer loyalty are advised to constantly interact with customers in ways of serving them better, as this study has proven the importance of service quality.
- 2) Money deposit banks are endeavored to create an environment that their service is fair and free from manipulation from special individuals, to make customers feel special and wanted. No customer should be treated differently.

Areas of further research

Some limitations to this study should be noted, and efforts to resolve them would serve as avenues for future research in this field. First the findings of the study may have limited generalizability. The sample which seemed appropriate for this particular study, was customers of five selected money deposit banks in port Harcourt. It would be more meaningful if the same findings hold consistent in different types of customers from other province across the country. Future research could investigate among customers of other service sections such as retail supermarkets and hospitals and even non-service sections to compare the results. It would be interesting as well to replicate these study foreign money deposit banks and their customers. This would help in documenting any difference across countries.

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